

Vat photopolymerization of biomimetic bone scaffolds based on Mg, Sr, Zn-substituted hydroxyapatite: Effect of sintering temperature

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ABSTRACT

In response to the urgent demand for innovative bone regeneration solutions, the focus of this study is to develop and characterize Mg, Sr, Zn-substituted calcium phosphate scaffolds that replicate the trabecular architecture of cancellous bone. Ion substitution represents a promising approach to improve the biological effectiveness of calcium phosphates and composite materials used in bone tissue engineering applications. Porous scaffolds mimicking the natural bone structure were additively manufactured from the photosensitive ceramic suspensions for vat photopolymerization using digital light processing. The impact of the selected trace elements (0, 1 and 5 mol.% substitution) and the sintering temperature (900, 1000, 1100, 1200, and 1300 °C) was investigated in relation to the obtained crystalline phase content, microstructure, elemental distribution, thermal stability, and mechanical properties. After sintering, in addition to hydroxyapatite, β -tricalcium phosphate was detected as a result of the added trace elements in the calcium-deficient hydroxyapatite used as a starting powder. The obtained scaffolds exhibited uniform distribution of the trace elements, and they feature 3D-designed porosity predominantly ranged from 10 to 900 μm in diameter, with an average pore size of $546.25 \pm 10.95 \mu\text{m}$. The total porosity of scaffolds was $76.24 \pm 1.32 \text{ vol}\%$ and an average wall thickness of $217.03 \pm 8.98 \mu\text{m}$, closely resembling the morphology of cancellous bone tissue. The mechanical properties of the scaffolds sintered at 1100 °C, 1200 °C, and 1300 °C were in line with those typically observed in trabecular bone. The study demonstrates the feasibility of using custom made bioactive hydroxyapatite powders together with vat photopolymerization to design the porosity and properties of the bone scaffolds on demand, based on the requirements of individual bone defects.

1. Introduction

The incidence of bone fractures is increasing globally, with consequential economic implications. Bone grafting, a surgical procedure conducted on a global scale with an annual case count exceeding 2 million, now stands as the second most prevalent tissue transplantation, exceeded only by blood transfusions [1]. The three primary bone grafting categories for treating critical sized bone defects (>2 cm) are

autografts, allografts, and bone graft substitutes. Autografts and allografts have limitations and come with associated risks such as donor site morbidity, postoperative pain, increased blood loss, infection and unpredictable bone quality [1–3]. In response to these limitations, over the past few decades the development of ideal synthetic bone scaffolds has been an active research area [1]. An optimal bone scaffold in bone tissue engineering must provide temporary mechanical support for surrounding tissues during bone regeneration while also promoting osteogenesis.

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Replicating the intricate mechanical characteristics, structural complexities, and biological functions of bone remains a significant challenge [4,5]. However, the new cutting-edge printing techniques are driving breakthroughs in the development of biomimetic scaffolds for bone regeneration, allowing the precise recreation of bone-like structures and the integration of key biological factors, leading to a new era in personalized scaffolds in bone tissue engineering [6–11].

Different additive manufacturing (AM) techniques show great promise in producing bone tissue engineering scaffolds [7–11]. The notable advantage of 3D-printed bone structures is the possibility of adjusting their shape and pore size, and thus improving their mechanical properties. Precise control over the production process and the ability to tailor final products make 3D printing technology particularly attractive for biomedical applications [6,12]. It is important to note that in the fabrication of porous bone scaffolds by 3D printing technology equiaxed square, round, or hexagonal channels interconnected with one another are used, and the scaffolds do not precisely replicate the structure of natural cancellous bone where the internal pore diameters and the diameters of the support walls are not uniform. The crucial factor in designing an appropriate scaffold lies in the ability to control the porosity, the pore connectivity, and the wall thickness diameter [13]. Ceramic vat polymerization has gained prominence in biomedical applications, particularly in the context of bone regeneration, owing to its capacity to fabricate intricate porous structures that closely mimic the native bone architecture, including precise control over pore size and interconnected porosity. The high precision of vat photopolymerization enables the fabrication of structures closely resembling natural bone tissue and therefore offers great potential to produce personalized patient solutions on demand including highly precise customized bone scaffolds [14,15]. Ceramic vat photopolymerization is an AM process that involves layer-by-layer fabrication of ceramic structures utilizing typically an ultraviolet (UV) or a visible light spectrum light source using ceramic resin composed of ceramic powder, liquid monomers, photoinitiators, and additives [12].

Among bioceramic materials, synthetic hydroxyapatite (HAp), stands prominently as an ideal candidate for the manufacture of bone scaffolds. This preference arises from its significant similarity in both composition and crystallographic structure to the primary bone constituent, bioapatite, which comprises of over 65 vol% of inorganic bone matrix. Due to its highly substituted structure, biological apatite with a Ca/P molar ratio less than 1.67, is called calcium-deficient carbonated HAp [16]. The flexible hexagonal structure of HAp can incorporate variety of ions (Na^+ , Mg^{2+} , K^+ , CO_3^{2-} , F^- , Cl^-) and mimic the chemical composition of natural bone tissue to further improve properties of fabricated scaffolds. The combined effects of two or more substituents on both the physicochemical and biological characteristics of HAp have been extensively studied. Multi-substituted HAp can be synthesized from either synthetic precursor supplemented with trace elements or biogenic sources. The incorporation of ionic substitutes can serve various purposes, including internal antibacterial action (e.g., Ag^+ , Zn^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , and F^-), stimulation of bone metabolism (e.g., Mg^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , Mn^{2+}), or potential anti-cancer properties (e.g., SeO_3^{2-} , SeO_4^{2-} , Fe^{3+}). By combining specific ions, the material properties required for a particular bone application can be adjusted to meet desired specifications [17,18]. In our previous work [19], chitosan-based composite scaffolds with added calcium phosphate (CaP), mainly HAp and octacalcium phosphate pentahydrate, mono-substituted with magnesium (Mg^{2+}), selenite (SeO_3^{2-}), strontium (Sr^{2+}) and zinc (Zn^{2+}) ions, were prepared by the freeze gelation method. The introduction of trace elements significantly enhanced osteogenic properties, as evidenced by the increased bone tissue formation and the upregulation of osteogenic marker genes in cultures with bone marrow-derived mesenchymal stem cells [19]. Sr^{2+} enhances the expression of alkaline phosphatase, collagen type I, runt-related transcription factor 2, and osteocalcin. Mg^{2+} ion function as growth factors during the initial stages of osteogenesis and bone growth, whereas Zn^{2+} ions play a vital role in alkaline phosphatase

expression and the creation of an alkaline environment conducive to the precipitation of CaPs and the mineralization of the extracellular matrix [20–24]. Incorporating trace elements into scaffolds offers the advantage of reducing the reliance on growth factors in scaffold design. This is advantageous because the use of growth factors can potentially lead to undesired ectopic bone formation and, if not carefully designed, may result in adverse side effects due to their rapid release [16]. However, the main drawback of such chitosan/CaP scaffolds is their poor mechanical properties, limiting their use in bone tissue engineering [19]. The core novelty in this work is the incorporation of the custom mono-phase HAp powders multi-substituted with trace elements into a photocurable resin and fabricating biomimetic scaffolds with designed porosity that mirrors the architecture of natural bone, with the potential to increase the load bearing capacity of the scaffold compared to, for example, freeze gelation technique utilized in Ref. [19].

Considering the significant importance of trace elements in bone regeneration [19,25,26], biomimetic approach was combined with the state-of-the-art technique of ceramic vat photopolymerization utilizing the DLP technique. In previous studies [27,28], we employed a wet precipitation method to mono-substitute Sr^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , and Zn^{2+} into multi-phase CaPs systems from biogenic source, examining substitution mechanisms and the properties of the resulting powders [27,28]. In this study, the powder preparation method was modified to achieve a multi-substituted (Sr^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , and Zn^{2+}) HAp phase without the precipitation of OCP. This adjustment was made due to the instability of the OCP phase at elevated temperatures required in processing of ceramic structures. In this study, novel photocurable resins containing HAp multi-substituted with Mg^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , and Zn^{2+} ions (0, 1 and 5 mol.%) were shaped into highly complex and porous scaffolds. The scaffolds used in bone regeneration must strike a delicate balance between providing adequate strength and maintaining optimal surface properties for cellular and tissue interactions. Sintering temperature plays a pivotal role in enhancing strength but can reduce bioactivity, bioresorption and specific surface area which can hinder biological performance and the regenerative process. Hence, the optimization of sintering temperature becomes a critical consideration, requiring meticulous attention to balance the mechanical robustness with the preservation of adequate scaffold characteristics. Accordingly, five different temperatures (900, 1000, 1100, 1200, and 1300 °C) were selected for sintering of the fabricated structures. The effects of the selected trace elements and the sintering temperatures were investigated regarding the crystalline phase content, elemental distribution, microstructure, thermal stability, and mechanical properties. Physicochemical and biological properties of cationic and anionic substituted HAp have been thoroughly examined in numerous studies, with well-documented positive effects on bone regeneration. However, to the best of our knowledge, this is the first time that trabecular bone biomimetic scaffolds based on substituted HAp were fabricated by the ceramic vat photopolymerization method. The results of this work present a novel avenue for the field of bone regeneration and redefine the boundaries of bone reconstruction.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Substituted HAp powder and ceramic slurry preparation

The multi-substituted (Sr^{2+} , Mg^{2+} and Zn^{2+}) and non-substituted reference HAp powders were synthesized by the wet precipitation method, following our previous studies [27,28] with slight modifications in synthesis parameters to obtain multi-substituted mono-phase HAp powder. In brief, HAp powders were prepared by dissolving strontium nitrate ($\text{Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2$), zinc nitrate hexahydrate ($\text{Zn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and magnesium chloride hexahydrate ($\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) in demineralized water at 40 °C. After ion precursors were fully dissolved, an appropriate amount of calcium oxide (CaO) was added at the same temperature, and the solution/suspension was stirred for 1 h. Subsequently, ammonium dihydrogen phosphate ($\text{NH}_4\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4$) was added to

solution to achieve a $(Ca + Sr + Zn + Mg)/P$ molar ratio 1.67, required for stoichiometric HAp. Stirring was continued for 10 h at 90 °C, followed by an overnight aging step at room temperature. The selected $(Sr + Zn + Mg)/(Ca + Sr + Zn + Mg)$ ratios were 1 and 5 mol%, and these samples were labeled as HAp_1MIX and HAp_5MIX, respectively, while non-substituted powder was labeled as HAp. The substitution of Sr^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , and Zn^{2+} ions in HAp_1MIX and HAp_5MIX were obtained in equal proportions, resulting in a substitution rate of 0.33 and 1.67 mol% for each individual element, respectively. After synthesis, the powders were filtered and dried at 90 °C.

Powders were wet-milled in ethanol using a planetary ball milling machine (Fritsch, Germany) for 2 h at a rotating speed of 200 rpm with zirconia milling balls of 0.5 cm in diameter. After milling, the powders were dried for 2 h at 90 °C. The dried powders were sintered at 800 °C with a heating rate of 10 °C/min from room temperature up to the sintering temperature, a dwell time of 2 h at the sintering temperature, and a cooling rate of 5 °C/min down to the room temperature. Sintering the powders at 800 °C was performed to serve the purposes of processing and slurry development. Obtained HAp_800, HAp_1MIX_800 and HAp_5MIX_800 powders were mixed with a commercial photocurable resin premix supplied by Lithoz GmbH in a volume % ratio of 38/62 as powder/resin.

2.2. CAD model, printing, debinding and sintering of HAp bioceramics

The highly porous structure, similar to that of trabecular bone, is a focal point in bone tissue engineering research. Vat polymerization technology enables precise fabrication of these biomimetic scaffolds. A CAD model (Fig. 1a–d) of the desired structure that mimic natural bone tissue was designed by using nTopology 3.35.2 software and exported as an .stl file to the slicer software of the 3D printer. The cylinder shape CAD models with outer dimensions of 6×6 mm, in diameter and height, were fabricated using the CeraFab 7500 (Lithoz GmbH) DLP vat photopolymerization printer with a layer thickness of 25 μ m. After printing, the as-fabricated structures were cleaned by air brush and a commercial cleaning agent LithaSol 80 (Lithoz GmbH). Subsequently, structures were immersed in LithaSol 80 and subjected to a low power ultrasonic bath for 5 min to remove any remaining uncured resin. Due to the complex porosity, this cleaning process was repeated twice to ensure that the inner part of the structure was properly cleaned of the uncured

resin.

In addition, solid cuboid sticks were fabricated using the synthesized powders and sintered at temperatures of 900, 1000, 1100, 1200, and 1300 °C to evaluate the sintering shrinkage in lateral x, y directions and the printing direction z (Table 1). Sintering shrinkage was then compensated in the CAD model to achieve scaffolds with consistent dimensions after sintering at different temperatures.

To produce a final ceramic component, it is essential to expose the as-fabricated structure to precise thermal treatment (debinding) for the elimination of the cured polymer, and subsequently to sintering, to produce a structure with the desired mechanical properties. The debinding and sintering schedules are shown in Fig. 1e. The same debinding process was used for all as-fabricated and cleaned samples, while sintering was performed at different temperatures (900, 1000, 1100, 1200, and 1300 °C) in a laboratory-scale muffle furnace (RHF1500, Carbolite Ovens Ltd., UK) in air atmosphere. The labels of the fabricated scaffolds obtained from prepared HAp powders (HAp_800, HAp_1MIX_800, and HAp_5MIX_800), sintered at various temperatures, are presented in Table 2.

2.3. Characterizations of prepared HAp powders and fabricated structures

2.3.1. Mineralogical phase analysis

Mineralogical phase analysis of as-prepared and sintered powders at 800 °C, as well as fabricated samples sintered at different temperatures was performed via X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis (Panalytical Empyrean multipurpose X-ray diffractometer, PANalytical B. V., the

Table 1

Shrinkage compensation factors at different temperatures in xy and z axes for cuboid test samples, where z is the printing direction.

Temperature (°C)	Shrinkage	
	xy	z
900	0.99	1.09
1000	1.04	1.15
1100	1.16	1.28
1200	1.25	1.39
1300	1.25	1.39

Fig. 1. (a) Side and (b) cross-section views of the CAD model of scaffold. The CAD model thin cross-sections imaged from (c) the x-axis direction and, (d) z-axis direction showing the topology of the designed porosity as in inset. (e) Debinding and sintering schedule of the heat treatment process employed to obtain the final sintered products.

Table 2
Labels of fabricated scaffolds sintered at different temperatures.

Sintering temperature (°C)	Used as-prepared powder		
	HAp_800	HAp_1MIX_800	HAp_5MIX_800
900	HAp_900	HAp_1MIX_900	HAp_5MIX_900
1000	HAp_1000	HAp_1MIX_1000	HAp_5MIX_1000
1100	HAp_1100	HAp_1MIX_1100	HAp_5MIX_1100
1200	HAp_1200	HAp_1MIX_1200	HAp_5MIX_1200
1300	HAp_1300	HAp_1MIX_1300	HAp_5MIX_1300

Netherlands) using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ ($\lambda = 0.15418$ nm) radiation. The X-ray generator was operated at 45 kV and 40 mA and diffractograms were recorded in a 2θ range of $20^\circ - 80^\circ$ with a step size of 0.02° , using a beam mask of 10 mm and a nickel beam filter. Phase identification was performed using the Panalytical HighScore Plus software (version 3.0.5) with the database of the International Centre for Diffraction Data (Database version 4.1065).

2.3.2. Microstructure and elemental analysis

The scaffold microstructures were analyzed after sintering using a scanning electron microscope (SEM, JSM-IT500LA, Jeol, Japan) at an accelerating voltage of 15 kV. Energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) was used to obtain comprehensive information on the elemental distribution of the as-prepared powders (HAp_800, HAp_1MIX_800 and HAp_5MIX_800) and of the fabricated scaffolds (HAp_1300, HAp_1MIX_1300, HAp_5MIX_1300) through a SEM-EDS technique (DrySDTM detector, Jeol). Prior to imaging, scaffolds were coated with a thin conducting carbon layer. In addition to SEM imaging, obtained scaffolds were imaged with a digital camera in micro imaging mode.

The microstructure properties of the samples were analyzed based on 3D X-ray microtomography (micro-CT) imaging as previously described in our study [29]. In brief, the samples were imaged using the Xradia MicroXCT-400 device (Zeiss, Pleasanton, USA). A pixel size of $5.64 \mu\text{m}$ was achieved with a 4x objective. The X-ray tube was operated at 60 kV with a current of 166 μA , and a total of 1601 projections were captured, each with an exposure time of 3 s.

The reconstructions were carried out using the XMReconstructor software, which employs the filtered back projection algorithm. A rectangular cuboid measuring $3700 \times 3700 \times 400 \mu\text{m}$ was selected from each sample for analysis. Porosities, open porosity, wall thickness and pore size distributions were calculated using ImageJ with the BoneJ plugin [30]. Interconnectivity was assessed using a custom MATLAB algorithm described in Ref. [31]. Image processing and visualizations were performed using Avizo 2022.1 software (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, USA).

2.3.3. Compression test

The obtained cylindrical scaffolds (6×6 mm, $n = 7$, where n is the number of samples) were tested under compression using a non-hydraulic universal material testing machine (Instron 5960, Instron Ltd.) at a constant applied displacement rate of 0.5 mm/min at room temperature ($T = 23.0 \text{ }^\circ\text{C} \pm 0.5$) at cross-sectional area. The compressive load and displacement were recorded at 0.1 s intervals during testing with a cell load of 2 kN. Maximum compressive engineering stress in respect to the whole sample diameter was determined using the software associated with the testing machine. The stress (σ) was calculated by dividing the applied force (F) by the cross-sectional area (A) of the scaffolds. Strain (ϵ) was calculated as the change in height (Δh) divided by the scaffold height (h_0). The Young's modulus in compression was determined as the slope of the initial linear range of stress-strain curves. The morphology of fractured scaffold after the compressive test was analyzed by SEM (JSM-IT500LA, Jeol). Prior to imaging, scaffolds were coated with a thin conducting layer of gold (S150 Sputter Coater, Edwards).

2.4. Statistical analysis

Quantitative results were presented as mean \pm standard deviation. Statistical analysis was conducted using a one-way analysis, with statistical significance denoted by $p < 0.05$ (*) when differences were observed.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Phase composition of as-prepared powders and fabricated scaffolds

In our previous studies [27,28], we investigated the phase content of multi-phase CaP powder systems obtained from biogenic source which were mono-substituted with Sr^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , and Zn^{2+} ions, both in their as-precipitated state and after heat treatment ($1200 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). In the current study, different phase compositions of obtained HAp powders after heat treatment are expected due to the modified synthesis and multi-substitution with selected ions (0, 1, and 5 mol.%). Fig. 2a depicts the XRD patterns of the as-prepared powders (HAp, HAp_1MIX, HAp_5MIX) and heat-treated powders at $800 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (HAp_800, HAp_1MIX_800, HAp_5MIX_800). The XRD peaks of the as-prepared powders closely match the line patterns for HAp (JCPDS No. 09-0431), as indicated by the reference patterns below the experimental data. After heat treatment at $800 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, HAp_800 powders exhibited a strong resemblance to the HAp pattern. However, in the case of HAp_1MIX_800 and HAp_5MIX_800 powders, additional peaks corresponding to β -tricalcium phosphate (β -TCP, JCPDS No. 09-0169) were observed, with higher peak intensity in the powder containing a higher substitution level of Sr^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , and Zn^{2+} ions. No additional peaks characteristic for strontium, magnesium, or zinc compounds were observed. EDS analysis was conducted to confirm the atomic composition of the powders heat-treated at $800 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The EDS elemental mapping (Fig. 2b) confirmed the presence and even distribution of calcium, phosphorus and magnesium in the HAp_800 powder, as well as the presence of calcium, phosphorus, strontium, zinc, and magnesium in HAp_1MIX_800 and HAp_5MIX_800 powders. EDS elemental mapping confirmed the presence of magnesium in the HAp_800 sample, despite the powder not being nominally substituted with Mg^{2+} ions. In our previous studies [28, 32], when synthetic sources of Ca^{2+} ions were used, HAp powders obtained from calcium carbonate or calcium oxide were substituted with 0.86 and 0.40 mol.% of Mg^{2+} ions, respectively. Synthetic sources contain ionic impurities depending on their origin, which may contribute to the presence of these elements in the resulting HAp powders. EDS spectrum of the HAp_800, HAp_1MIX_800 and HAp_5MIX_800 powders are shown in Fig. S1a of Supporting Information. Our previous studies [27,28] have shown that substitutions up to 5 mol.% of Sr^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , and Zn^{2+} ions in CaPs are noncytotoxic and promote cell proliferation. Single-substituted HAp bone grafts have exhibited improved biological efficacy *in vitro* and *in vivo*. However, they frequently fall short in meeting the multifaceted demands of clinical applications. Hence, it is reasonable to hypothesize that utilizing multi-substituted HAp may further augment the advantageous effects of each individual substitute [25]. Multiple ionic substitutions in CaPs have shown a collective synergistic effect on bone cell growth, collagen type I expression and the mineral formation capacity of the human mesenchymal stem cells [17].

Fig. 2c represents the XRD patterns of the fabricated scaffolds sintered at various temperatures. The XRD patterns of HAp_900, HAp_1000, HAp_1100, and HAp_1200 scaffolds closely match the line patterns for crystalline HAp (JCPDS No. 09-0432). Alongside the HAp peaks, a small peak characteristic of β -TCP is also observed. In the XRD pattern of the HAp_1300 scaffold, in addition to HAp and β -TCP peaks, there is a small, distinctive peak corresponding to α -tricalcium phosphate (α -TCP, JCPDS No.09-0348). The XRD patterns of HAp_1MIX_900, HAp_1MIX_1000, HAp_1MIX_1100, HAp_1MIX_1200, and HAp_1MIX_1300 scaffolds exhibit similar patterns, featuring peaks associated with HAp and β -TCP. As for the XRD patterns of HAp_5MIX_900, HAp_5MIX_1000,

Fig. 2. (a) X-ray diffraction data of as-prepared (HAp, HAp_1MIX, and HAp_5MIX) and sintered powders at 800 °C (HAp_800, HAp_1MIX_800, and HAp_5MIX_800). (b) EDS element mapping of the HAp_800, HAp_1MIX_800, and HAp_5MIX_800 powder samples. Scale bar: 5 μ m. (c) X-ray diffraction data of fabricated scaffolds sintered at different temperatures. The standard JCPDS card data for hydroxyapatite (HAp, black) and β -tricalcium phosphate (β -TCP, red) are provided below to the obtained X-ray diffraction data. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

HAp_5MIX_1100, HAp_5MIX_1200, and HAp_5MIX_1300 scaffolds, they share similarities with the XRD patterns of scaffolds derived from HAp_1MIX powder. However, there is a notable increase in the intensity of the characteristic β -TCP peaks, especially at higher sintering temperatures of 1200 and 1300 °C.

Despite of its excellent biocompatibility, HAp sintered at high-temperature is not an ideal biomaterial. It lacks biodegradability and exhibits low bioactivity. Stoichiometric and highly crystalline HAp resists dissolution induced by the osteoclasts, preventing bone remodeling, and persisting within the bone defect for extended periods [33]. Studies have shown that biphasic CaP systems composed of HAp and β -TCP are promising alternatives for achieving materials with improved biodegradation. These CaP systems are able to promote a rapid biomaterial replacement and a better connection with the bone tissue [34]. The heat treatment of scaffolds obtained from the HAp_800 powder, without substituents, resulted in a predominance of HAp as the main phase with small amount of β -TCP and α -TCP (α -TCP only after heat treatment at 1300 °C). According to Krajewski et al. [35] stoichiometric HAp, free of ionic impurities, exhibits remarkable stability up to

1400 °C, while at higher temperatures transition to the tricalcium phosphate phase begins. The increased amount of β -TCP is a common occurrence during the thermal treatment of non-stoichiometric, calcium-deficient HAp at temperatures exceeding 700 °C [36]. As reported in our previous study [27], the quantitative phase analysis of the heat-treated CaP powders demonstrated that an increase in Zn^{2+} and Mg^{2+} substitution levels lead to the stabilization of the β -TCP phase. Both HAp_1MIX_800 and HAp_5MIX_800 represent multi-substituted systems, characterized as non-stoichiometric HAp with a Ca/P ratio lower than 1.67. Ion substituents in HAp induce significant lattice strain. This results in the transformation of HAp into TCP phases at lower temperatures compared to stoichiometric HAp [27,35,37,38]. In non-substituted HAp_800 powder, the presence of impurities such as magnesium, detected by EDS, can lead to the formation of small amounts of β -TCP and α -TCP phases after heat treatment. α -TCP was not detected in the scaffolds obtained from powders HAp_1MIX_800 and HAp_5MIX_800 due to stabilizing effect of substituted ions on β -TCP phase. The aim of enhancing the biodegradation rate of HAp has led to the development of biphasic CaP, which combines stable HAp with more

soluble β -TCP since the late 1980s [33]. In this study, biphasic CaP system was obtained by substituting therapeutic trace elements (Sr^{2+} , Mg^{2+} and Zn^{2+}) and obtaining calcium-deficient HAp. The obtained systems should provide scaffolds with better bioactivity and bioresorption, especially scaffolds obtained from HAp_5MIX_800 powder and sintered at lower temperatures.

3.2. Microstructure of sintered scaffolds fabricated using ceramic vat photopolymerization

SEM micrographs depicting the structure of fabricated HAp_1300, HAp_1MIX_1300, and HAp_5MIX_1300 scaffolds are shown in Fig. 3a. As anticipated, there are no observable differences in the microstructures among scaffolds derived from HAp_800, HAp_1MIX_800, and HAp_5MIX_800 powders sintered at 1300 °C. EDS elemental mapping (Fig. 3b) further validates the uniform distribution of elements following sintering at the highest temperature. Ensuring the even distribution of substituted ions is crucial to achieve consistent biomaterial properties across the entire scaffold, essential for its optimal regenerative potential. Upon closer examination at higher magnification, the sintered grains in the HAp_1MIX_1300 and HAp_5MIX_1300 scaffolds exhibit noticeable similarities. However, in the HAp_1300 scaffold, grain boundaries remain undetectable. It is worth noting that magnesium, which was present in powders HAp_800, was not detected in the HAp_1300 scaffold. EDS spectrum of the HAp_1300, HAp_1MIX_1300 and HAp_5MIX_1300 scaffolds are shown in Fig. S1b of Supporting Information.

Scaffolds fabricated from HAp_5MIX_800 powder were selected to present a representative scaffold morphology and microstructure characteristics at different sintering temperatures. The morphology analysis (Fig. 4a) reveals highly porous structures in the HAp_5MIX_900, HAp_5MIX_1000, HAp_5MIX_1100, HAp_5MIX_1200, and HAp_5MIX_1300 scaffolds. All fabricated scaffolds exhibit highly porous structures characterized by open and interconnected pores. Uncured slurry presents difficulties in cleaning small and interconnected pores within scaffolds. Cross-sectional views (Fig. 4a) affirm the thorough

cleaning of the scaffolds, despite the complexity of their structure. The inclusion (impurity) of trace amounts of manganese in HAp results in a blue coloration after sintering at elevated temperatures in an oxidizing environment, and, as the sintering temperature increases, the blue colour in the scaffolds intensifies. This change is attributed to the oxidation of manganese ions within HAp's unique crystal structure [39]. The EDS analysis did not detect manganese in the obtained powders or scaffolds sintered at 1300 °C. It is likely that the manganese ions in such small quantities are not detectable by EDS.

As seen in Fig. 4b, at lower magnifications, there are no discernible differences among the microstructure of the obtained scaffolds sintered at different temperatures. At higher magnification, the effect of sintering temperature on grain size and surface porosity become more apparent. The internal porosity between particles related to the processing was not determined in this study. In the scaffold HAp_5MIX_900, solid state diffusion has not yet fully activated, and the powder particles remain as discrete units and are not yet physically interconnected. The following neck growth is more pronounced in scaffold HAp_5MIX_1000. In scaffold HAp_5MIX_1100, the material densification stage is observed in parallel with evident grain growth. The internal porosity steadily decreases as the grains continue to grow. Finally, in the case of scaffolds HAp_5MIX_1200 and HAp_5MIX_1300, the concluding stage of sintering is reached, characterized by the closure of the remaining pores [33]. As expected, the mechanisms related to grain growth are dominant in the final stage of the sintering, and therefore grain size increased in scaffolds HAp_5MIX_1300 compared to the scaffolds HAp_5MIX_1200.

The quality of the final components can be influenced by the thermal debinding conditions. Therefore, precise adjustment of process parameters such as heating rate, dwelling time, and sintering temperature is crucial. During binder decomposition at elevated temperatures, cracks may develop due to the release of carbon dioxide (CO_2) generated from the decomposition of the polymer binder [40]. No cracking or delamination was observed in the microstructures of the sintered scaffolds. This indicates that wall thickness was correctly selected to allow decomposition gases to exit the structure without increasing the internal pressure.

Fig. 3. (a) Scanning electron microscope micrographs of prepared scaffolds HAp_1300, HAp_1MIX_1300 and HAp_5MIX_1300. Scale bar: 500 μm. (b) EDS element mapping of the HAp_1300, HAp_1MIX_1300, and HAp_5MIX_1300 scaffolds. Scale bar: 5 μm.

Fig. 4. (a) Morphology and (b) microstructure of fabricated scaffolds (HAp_5MIX) sintered at different temperatures. Scale bar: 200 and 5 μm .

Key parameters when designing porous scaffolds are open porosity, total porosity, pore curvature, pore diameter and wall thickness [41]. The micro-CT analysis of scaffolds (Fig. 5a) was used to determine pore size distribution (Fig. 5b) and proportion of open porosity compared to the overall porosity as a function of certain sized particles that can enter the scaffold (Fig. 5c). The results of porosity, average pore size and wall thickness measurements are summarized in Table 3. Pores size in scaffolds ranges mostly from 10 to 900 μm except for scaffold HAp_5MIX_1000 where the pore size ranges from 10 to 1100 μm . The reason for the larger pore size range observed in the scaffold HAp_5MIX_1000 is likely not to printing errors, but probably handling or measurement discrepancies. Nonetheless, this outcome does not significantly impact the conclusions of the current study. Total porosities of the scaffolds were similar with average of 76.24 ± 1.32 vol%, mimicking the morphology of cancellous bone tissue. Similar average pore size and wall thickness were determined between the samples with average of 546.25 ± 10.95 and 217.03 ± 8.98 μm , respectively. However, regular decrease in the wall thickness is observed from 216.16 ± 52.81 at 900 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to 194.93 ± 42.33 at 1300 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, due to sintering densification and the following shrinkage. The wall thickness refers to the thickness of the connecting elements in a porous structure. It is highly correlated with the compressive strength and inversely related to the total porosity, which, in turn, influences cell penetration and tissue growth within the

scaffold. Achieving an optimal wall thickness is essential to ensure suitable mechanical properties while maintaining the necessary porosity [42]. The similarities between scaffold microstructure sintered at different temperatures, in terms of porosity and pore size, indicate successful shrinkage compensation during the fabrication process.

The architecture of the scaffold can be described by a set of structural parameters that play a key role in achieving optimal biological performance [41]. The open porosity refers to the structural arrangement in which pores are interconnected, forming a network that facilitates the infiltration and integration of cells or particles seeded onto the scaffold. The proportion of open porosity in relation to the total porosity serves as an indicator of interconnectivity, and when coupled with data on pore dimensions, this ratio offers valuable insights into the proportion of pores that are accessible to particles (e.g. cells) of a specific size (Fig. 5c) [31]. The size of mesenchymal stem cells is in the range of 15–30 μm [43]. When studying cell seeding, it is worth noting that particle sizes up to 200 μm are of primary relevance. This size range allows migration of small cell aggregates in the seeding process. Dense cell aggregates, known as spheroids, have demonstrated superior tissue formation and cell viability compared to individual cells [31]. As shown in Fig. 5c–a 50 μm particle is able to infiltrate into all pores in fabricated scaffolds, while a 200 μm particle is able to infiltrate into 98 % of the pores.

Interconnectivity of pores is imperative for facilitating the diffusion

Fig. 5. (a) Micro-CT images of the sintered scaffolds (scale bar: 1 mm) along with the associated (b) pore size distribution by density (%) as a function of different pore diameter ranges (μm). (c) The relationship between open porosity/total porosity (%) and particle size, as determined through the analysis of micro-CT images of the scaffolds. Vertical red dashed lines indicate how many pores can be infiltrated by particles of 50 and 200 μm in size. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

of essential nutrients, oxygen, and extracellular fluids into and out of the cellular matrix. Pore sizes ranging from 100 to 400 μm foster osteogenesis by promoting cell migration, the formation of cell-cell networks, vascularization, nutrient supply, and the diffusion of metabolic waste. On the other hand, pores smaller than 100 μm , are essential for tasks such as cell seeding and retention, the growth of capillaries, and interactions between the cells and the extracellular matrix [44]. However, in the literature, varying information regarding the optimal pore size can be found. Xia et al. [45] reported that pores $<200 \mu\text{m}$ within the scaffold promote the formation of densely populated blood vessels with small diameters in the surrounding area. Conversely, pores $>200 \mu\text{m}$ appear to facilitate the growth of sparsely distributed blood vessels with larger diameters when observing in deeper inside of the scaffold. It appears that both small and large pores play distinct roles in vascularization, and scaffolds incorporating both pore sizes may be conducive to effective vascularization [45]. Choi et al. [46] found that scaffolds with pore sizes $<200 \mu\text{m}$, when implanted *in vivo*, favoured the formation of smaller blood vessels at higher densities and poor penetration depth of the vessels, while at pore sizes $>200 \mu\text{m}$, lower density of larger blood vessels were developed deep inside the scaffolds. According to Feng et al. [47], the growth of blood vessels is favoured by larger pore sizes, whereas pores smaller than 400 μm hinder growth, resulting in reduced blood vessel diameters. Although a pore size of 100 μm is acceptable, it is suggested that an average pore size of at least 300 μm is preferable for promoting new bone formation. Additionally, a pore size of 400 μm is considered optimal for vascularization during osteogenesis [47]. Furthermore, specialized studies have indicated that scaffold pore sizes larger than 390 μm , with an upper limit of 590 μm , are more effective in enhancing bone tissue formation [41]. The study conducted by Wang et al. [48] reveals that porous, metal-based, scaffolds, characterized by a tailored pore size of 1000 μm , exhibits a superior effectiveness in promoting the attachment, proliferation, and osteogenic differentiation of bone marrow-derived stem/stromal cells when compared to scaffolds with smaller pore sizes. Additionally, scaffolds featuring an irregular porous structure demonstrated improvements on various aspects of bone marrow-derived stem/stromal cell behaviour, including adhesion, proliferation, differentiation, bone formation, ingrowth, and blood vessel formation, in contrast to their regular porous counterparts. The expression levels of vascular endothelial growth factor and kinase insert domain receptor within these irregular-structured scaffolds significantly surpassed those observed in scaffolds with smaller pore sizes and uniform pore shapes, underscoring the role of pore size and structure in regulating the expression of angiogenesis-related genes. The study [48] underscores the significance of replicating the microstructure found in natural bone tissue, emphasizing the advantages of irregular-structured scaffolds with larger pore sizes over those with uniform pore characteristics. Supporting these findings, in the study done by Liang et al. [49], it was demonstrated that the irregular pores in scaffold created a diverse mechanical stimulation environment, encompassing micro deformations, efficient mass transport, fluid shear stress, and enhanced diffusion of biological factors. This multifaceted environment better aligned with the requirements for osteogenic mechanical stimulation, resulting in the trabecular-like scaffold and demonstrating superior osteogenic capabilities compared to the scaffold with regular pore shape [49].

In the present study, the wide range of pore size with irregular shape in the fabricated scaffolds demonstrates the potential of ceramic vat

Table 3

The porosity parameters of the composite scaffolds based on micro-CT image data.

scaffold	porosity (%)	average pore size (μm)	wall thickness (μm)
HAp_5MIX_900	75.55	551.94 ± 133.55	216.16 ± 52.81
HAp_5MIX_1000	74.83	536.05 ± 135.45	214.59 ± 52.31
HAp_5MIX_1100	75.54	532.79 ± 126.94	208.24 ± 55.60
HAp_5MIX_1200	77.43	554.54 ± 131.01	201.21 ± 48.98
HAp_5MIX_1300	77.84	555.93 ± 133.41	194.93 ± 42.33

photopolymerization to fulfil the structural requirements needed for tissue regeneration. Ceramic vat photopolymerization offers the unique capability to fabricate trabecular-like scaffolds with a high degree of precision and complexity. This technology enables the creation of intricate three-dimensional structures that resemble the structure of trabecular bone in the natural human skeleton.

3.3. Mechanical properties

To determine the effect of ion substitutions and sintering temperatures on mechanical properties of the scaffold, compression tests were conducted on all the fabricated scaffolds. The stress-strain curves of scaffolds fabricated using the ceramic resin with the HAp_5MIX_800 powder, and sintered at different temperatures, are shown in Fig. 6a, and the morphology of the fractured surfaces after compression test are

shown in Fig. 6b. These results can be considered representative since there was no significant difference between scaffolds fabricated from different powder types i.e. HAp_800, HAp_1MIX_800 and HAp_5MIX_800.

Scaffolds HAp_5MIX_900 and HAp_5MIX_1000 exhibit typical stress-strain curves for porous biological scaffolds where the strength was repeatedly lost and recovered as each layer of walls collapsed. Sawtooth-like behavior in the mechanical properties of porous scaffolds refers to a pattern where stress-strain curves exhibit a series of repeated peaks and valleys, resembling the shape of a saw blade as seen in Fig. 6a. This behavior can be related to the arrangement, interaction, or failure of structural elements within the scaffold, such as walls, pores, or interfaces. This behavior often occurs due to the hierarchical or complex structure of porous materials [50,51]. Initially, elastic stress increases linearly. With further compression, a multi-peak profile with sawtooth-like behavior emerges, attributed to the consecutive wall failures under elastic stress. When the stress within a wall exceed the characteristic fracture stress of the material, the wall fails. Importantly, the wall failure does not lead to a complete structural collapse but results in a minor release of overall elastic stress, quickly recovering as displacement increases. In contrast, scaffolds HAp_5MIX_1100, HAp_5MIX_1200, and HAp_5MIX_1300 exhibit linear elastic deformation followed by brittle failure of the whole structure.

These results can be correlated with the fracture surface analysis in Fig. 6b. This analysis revealed distinct trends in relation to the sintering

Fig. 6. (a) Experimental stress-strain response. (b) Microstructures of the cracks after compressive strength analysis. Scale bar: 20 and 1 μm .

temperatures used for scaffold fabrication. In the case of scaffolds HAp_5MIX_900 and HAp_5MIX_1000, a granular, poorly sintered, structure was evident within the fractured surfaces. This feature is attributed to the application of lower sintering temperatures, which, in turn, resulted in diminished mechanical properties for these scaffolds. In the scaffold HAp_5MIX_1100, the partially sintered grains seen within the fractured surface were observed. While this partial sintering contributed to an increase in mechanical properties, it also produced a more distinctly sudden failure of the samples. Logically, scaffolds HAp_5MIX_1200 and HAp_5MIX_1300 exhibited fully sintered structures, significantly enhanced mechanical properties, and a more sudden failure mode. These observations underscore the intricate relationship between sintering temperature, resulting microstructure, and the mechanical behavior of the scaffolds. Understanding these connections is crucial for tailoring scaffold properties to specific applications.

The compressive strength of the porous scaffolds was assessed in terms of the measured fracture stress (Fig. 7a), while the linear elastic region was used to calculate the Young's modulus (Fig. 7b). For the sintering temperature of 900 °C, the average compressive strength across all fabricated scaffolds ranged from 0.36 to 0.50 MPa. At 1000 °C, this range increased to 0.41–0.82 MPa, followed by 1.10–1.90 MPa at 1100 °C, 2.30–2.76 MPa at 1200 °C, and 1.32–3.37 MPa at 1300 °C. Standard deviations of obtained compressive strength are presented in Fig. 7a. Generally, the compressive strength exhibited an upward trend with increasing sintering temperature, except for the scaffolds HAp_1300 and HAp_5MIX_1300. For scaffold HAp_5MIX_1300, the

decline in compressive strength compared to scaffold HAp_5MIX_1200 can be linked to the phase composition, as β -TCP was found to be the primary inorganic phase, as indicated by XRD results. This observation aligns with the findings of Impens et al. [52], where a decrease in HAp content in a HAp/ β -TCP biphasic CaP system led to reduced mechanical strength and Young's modulus, ranging from 10.1 to 0.4 MPa and 9.46 to 0.27 GPa, respectively.

In the field of biomechanical research, pertaining to scaffolds in bone tissue engineering, Young's modulus is considered a critical material property, alongside with the essential requirement for sufficient compressive strength to bear osteogenic loads during the healing process. The Young's modulus of the scaffolds increases as a function of sintering temperature, mirroring the trend observed for compressive strength. At the sintering temperature of 900 °C, the Young's modulus falls within the range of 20.52–31.39 MPa for all the fabricated scaffolds. At 1000 °C, this range increases to 28.83–58.48 MPa, followed by 62.23–98.56 MPa at 1100 °C, 105.26–129.51 MPa at 1200 °C, and 72.61–165.95 MPa at 1300 °C. Standard deviations of obtained Young's modulus are presented in Fig. 7b. It is worth noting that the mechanical properties of bone exhibit a wide range of reported values, influenced by factors such as local tissue density and testing conditions. Cancellous (trabecular) bone exhibits the Young's modulus in the range of 0.1–1.0 GPa and the strength that varies from 1 to 10 MPa. Despite this significant variability in the reported mechanical characteristics of bone, these values serve as a valuable reference for establishing the necessary mechanical properties for a scaffold [53]. The mechanical properties of the scaffolds sintered at 1100, 1200 and 1300 °C are in accordance with the mechanical properties typically observed in trabecular bone. High sintering temperatures result in low bioactivity and bioresorption of the scaffolds, leading to a non-ideal biomaterial. However, given the significant presence of β -TCP in scaffolds derived from HAp_5MIX_800 powder, higher sintering temperatures may be considered favourable for application in bone tissue engineering for this material.

It is challenging to precisely determine the effect of the substituted ions on mechanical properties of the scaffolds. As reported in our previous studies [27,54], non-substituted HAp powder demonstrated agglomerates of a plate-like morphology arranged in a “flower” shape, while after substitution with Sr^{2+} , Mg^{2+} and Zn^{2+} ions, the characteristic flower-shaped crystals are no longer visible and smaller clusters are observed as ions significantly inhibits the growth and size of HAp clusters. As a result of its greater surface area, smaller HAp crystals exhibit improved sinterability and densification, which also improves its mechanical properties due to smaller number of defects [55]. Therefore, the different morphology and size of substituted HAp crystals can have a relatively large effect on final mechanical properties of the scaffolds, as also indicated by our results shown in Fig. 7. Further, sintered scaffolds obtained from the HAp_5MIX_800 powders have significantly more β -TCP phase, compared to the scaffolds obtained from HAp_800 and HAp_1MIX_800 powders. Different phases in the structure significantly affect mechanical properties of the scaffolds as due to their different characteristics. Ion substitutions affect the phase composition, crystal structure and solubility of CaPs, and the weight ratio of different CaPs in the material. The increased weight ratio of β -TCP in HAp/ β -TCP systems alter the scaffolds degradability, mechanical properties and biological activity [56]. In a previous study [57], mechanical analyses were performed on CHT/HAp scaffolds obtained by freeze-gelation method. The compressive modulus of 4.8 ± 0.7 kPa, notably lower than the typical compressive modulus of bone, was determined. This suggests that the freeze-gelated scaffolds are suitable only for small-size bone defects in non-load-bearing applications. The primary objective of this study was to fabricate biomimetic bone scaffolds that incorporate therapeutic trace elements within the inorganic phase while ensuring suitable mechanical properties for load-bearing applications.

In order to avoid the previously mentioned negative side-effects related to high sintering temperatures, scaffolds sintered at lower temperatures (≤ 900 °C) are of great interest for treating critical-sized bone

Fig. 7. (a) Compressive strength and (b) Young's modulus of sintered scaffolds as a function of sintering temperature. The significant difference between two groups: * $p < 0.05$.

defects. However, when comparing to natural bone their limited mechanical properties make them unsuitable for load-bearing applications. In Fig. 8, a possible solution is presented, where porous scaffolds obtained in this study are positioned in a porous cage. The applicability of this scaffold type extends to load-bearing applications in bone tissue engineering, offering versatility across different anatomical regions in the human body. The same approach can be used for bi-phasic (HAp/ β -TCP) scaffolds sintered at higher temperatures to further improve mechanical properties. The cage should be made from biodegradable materials with appropriate mechanical properties. It should also be porous, allowing migration of cells and the diffusion of nutrients, metabolic waste, and oxygen through the porous scaffold. In addition, the cage must possess controlled biodegradable properties, while the ceramic scaffold should be designed for controlled bioresorption. This will enable the scaffold to degrade as the tissue regenerates, avoiding the requirement for supplementary removal surgeries. Current state-of-the-art technology in bone augmentation procedures often involves the use of a titanium mesh that supports an injected bioactive ceramic paste or autologous bone during bone defect regeneration. However, in this solution, the metallic scaffold needs to be removed in a second operation, significantly increasing costs and posing risks of negative effects on the patient's well-being [58]. An ideal material for cage fabrication could be synthetic biodegradable polymers such as poly(ϵ -caprolactone) (PCL) or polylactic acid (PLA), which are often utilized as biomaterials in bone tissue regeneration [59,60]. While PCL and PLA serve as scaffolds for tissue engineering due to their biodegradability and biocompatibility, achieving bioactivity or osteogenic properties often involves modifications such as incorporating bioactive molecules, growth factors, or surface modifications to induce osteogenesis or enhance bone regeneration. However, even if these polymers lack osteogenic properties, their biodegradability and biocompatibility make them ideal candidates for the described purpose in this study [61]. A porous scaffold based on PCL with a maximum compressive strength of approximately 120 MPa and a compressive modulus of about 325 MPa was fabricated by Aveiranov et al. [62]. Additionally, Zhou et al. [60] investigated various scaffold designs using PLA, with compressive stresses ranging from 16.04 MPa to 41.38 MPa and Young's moduli from 0.15 GPa to 0.28 GPa. Both studies demonstrated that these polymers possess mechanical properties suitable for load-bearing applications in bone tissue engineering.

4. Conclusions

The primary objective of this study was to manufacture a biomimetic scaffold that replicates bone microstructure, as well as the phase structure, and element content. In summary, ceramic vat photopolymerization with digital light processing was employed to fabricate trabecular-like porous scaffolds based on custom HAp powders substituted with 1 mol.% and 5 mol.% of Sr^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , and Zn^{2+} ions. The substituted HAp powders were prepared using the wet precipitation method, and the resulting fabricated scaffolds were sintered at five different temperatures (900, 1000, 1100, 1200, and 1300 °C).

The mechanical properties of the scaffolds sintered at 1100, 1200, and 1300 °C align with those typically observed in trabecular bone, where scaffold HAp_1MIX_1300 showed the highest mechanical properties. Micro-CT analysis revealed that scaffolds microstructure characteristics, closely resembling the morphology of cancellous bone tissue and confirmed that ceramic vat photopolymerization is a suitable technique for fabricating highly complex trabecular-like structures for bone regeneration purposes. Substitution of trace elements in starting HAp powder resulted in a biphasic CaP (HAp/ β -TCP) system after sintering that can lead to better bioactivity *in vivo*. The effect of substituted ions and sintering temperatures on the biological properties of scaffolds will be carried out in our future study. In addition, it is important to note that this study focused on a single scaffold microstructure type, and future investigations will explore printing porous scaffolds with smaller pore size ranges, to solve challenges associated with cleaning such

Fig. 8. This illustration offers a visual representation of the solution for scaffolds with low mechanical properties. The scaffold from our study, displayed in blue, is positioned within a white porous polymer-based cage. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

intricate structures.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Antonia Ressler: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Project administration, Resources, Validation, Writing – original draft. **Setareh Zakeri:** Formal analysis, Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Joana Dias:** Formal analysis. **Markus Hannula:** Formal analysis. **Jari Hyttinen:** Resources. **Hrvoje Ivanković:** Resources. **Marica Ivanković:** Resources, Writing – review & editing. **Susanna Miettinen:** Conceptualization, Supervision. **Martin Schwentenwein:** Conceptualization, Resources. **Erkki Levänen:** Resources, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Erkka J. Frankberg:** Supervision, Validation, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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